

A Novel Observation on Electrolysis of Dye Solutions : Formation of One or More Sharp Boundaries

SANTI R. PALIT

Department of Physical Chemistry,
Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-32

Received 20 June 1972

On passing a small current through a dye solution in a U-tube, a sharp boundary is seen to appear at the bottom of the cathode limb after some time depending on the nature of the dye, concentration, current strength, cell geometry, pH, added electrolyte and so on. The boundary is generally between a deep coloured acidic anode solution and a light coloured alkaline cathode solution. Acid dyes, particularly sulphonic acid dyes which are not acid-base indicators, are more prone to show such electrophoretic boundary formation than basic dyes. The boundary does not move with the current but remains stationary. On switching off the current the boundary disappears in a few hours or overnight which is very much faster than ordinary diffusion. If the current is continued for long, the cathode colour gets discharged in a few hours and the deep anode colour gets rather slowly discharged both usually to a water-white colour.

A surprising observation is that if such electrolysis is carried out in a double-bent U-tube (i.e., containing two U-bends), two very sharp boundaries inside the two inner tubes appear, dividing the solution into three zones : (1) acidic dark-coloured anode solution, (2) neutral colourless middle solution and (3) alkaline light coloured cathode solution. Many inorganic salts, particularly those with large coloured anions also show such boundary and/or double boundary formation.

No explanation even for the basic observation of inhibition of ionic migration after boundary formation is apparent. The anode solution evidently is the dye acid whose anion transport number has been reduced to zero for no apparent reason; it appears that the current is practically wholly transported by H^+ and OH^- ions probably by relay mechanism. It is also pointed out that at such low dilution and current density electronic conduction may also have a role.

Electrolysis at low concentration and low current density shows some anomalous features¹ which appear to be quite unexpected from the classical view of ion transport. On using ionic dyes as electrolytes so that ion transport could be visually followed, a novel feature was noticed and this is reported in this preliminary communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

The novel feature in question is the formation of one or more sharp boundaries with many interesting properties on electrolysis of solutions of dyes, particularly those containing— SO_3Na group. This is easily observed on electrolysis of say, xylydine ponceau or Evan's blue in a U-tube (Fig. 1). About 5 mg of Evan's blue or 10 mg of xylydine ponceau

per 100 cc water is a convenient concentration to be used in a U-tube of say, 22 mm O.D. and 30 cm height. On sending a direct current of about 2 ma through the solution, the anodic solution is observed to become progressively darker in colour and the cathodic solution lighter in colour. In the course of half an hour to a couple of hours a sharp boundary forms somewhere near BB', apparently between two solutions, one of darker colour (AB) and another of much lighter colour (CB). Each of these two solutions has the same depth of colour throughout. None of the aforementioned size, concentration or current strength is critical, and a wide variation yields more or less similar results. Furthermore, no matter where the dye solution is introduced in the U-tube the rest being water, the final position on electrolysis is always as described above.

Fig. 1

The zone AB is acidic (pH : near about 2.5) and CB is alkaline (pH : near about 11.5) and so the boundary may be thought of as the meeting place between the acidic anode solution and alkaline cathode solution. This is however not the whole story for the following reasons. Firstly, only a few dyes show this sharp boundary formation between a deeper anodic colour and a lighter cathodic colour, which are not necessarily the acid colour and the alkali colour of the dye. In fact, many of the dyes which show such sharp boundary formation have no separate acid and alkali colour. Secondly, most indicator dyes, including those which have sulphonic acid groups do not form such a sharp boundary but form only a diffuse interpenetrating boundary, if at all, between the acid colour and the alkaline colour. There are many other interesting properties associated with such boundary formation to be discussed below which make such a simple idea untenable. Of these a spectacular one is the formation of two sharp boundaries (see later) instead of one as above when the electrolysis is conducted in a doubly bent U-tube. Anyway, it is quite surprising to find that the dye anions do not at all move in an electric field as seen by the immobility of the boundary or boundaries (in the case of double boundary formation) though the current would be passing.

On continuing the electrolysis, the boundary remains practically stationary but the cathode solution slowly gets bleached to a water-white colour in a short time of a couple of hours or so. On prolonging the electrolysis still further, the anode solution also gets

progressively bleached and become practically colourless overnight, the boundary all through remaining in fact, nay, often getting sharper with time. The interesting thing about this bleaching is that it is apparently observed to take place throughout both AB and CB homogeneously and not at the electrodes. It is difficult to understand how the dye molecules which supposedly get reduced and oxidised at the cathode and anode respectively, could diffuse so fast inside the respective zones to give the appearance of homogeneous disappearance of colour.

On the other hand if after formation of the boundary the current is switched off, the two phases interdiffuse and in a comparatively short time say, a few hours to overnight, the whole solution becomes homogeneous. It is worthy of notice that this diffusion is much faster than ordinary diffusion. As a matter of fact, if a boundary is formed by careful manipulation between a dye solution below and water above it, the boundary remains fairly sharp for days with hardly any interdiffusion. It appears that there is a mutual attraction between the two layers. This is further seen from the queer fact that if some solution is slowly pipetted out from the anode zone AB, the boundary tends to remain at the same place BB' instead of undergoing a corresponding displacement towards A.

Effect of Concentration and pH : With increasing concentration of the same dye under otherwise identical condition, the boundary takes a longer time to make a discernable appearance. With xyloidine ponceau while the boundary appears in less than a couple of hours under the usual condition of say 10 mg/100 ml it takes more than 24 hours for a concentration of 50 mg/100 ml in the same U-tube. The same trend is found to be true for Evan's blue or any other dye which is capable of forming such boundary.

If the pH of the dye solution is adjusted to different values (pH : 4 to 11) it is found that alkaline pH has a definite retarding effect on the appearance of the boundary. Acids however have a strong effect on boundary formation. Firstly, the boundary tends to form nearer to the cathode; so much so, that at very low pH (e.g., dye in $N/10$ H_2SO_4) the boundary finally forms near about the middle of the cathode limb. Also, the boundary instead of making a sudden appearance at BB' starts moving downwards from the top of the cathode limb until it reaches the limiting position as mentioned above, the boundary being a colourless solution over a deeply coloured one as contrasted with the usual one composed of a lightly coloured solution over a deeply coloured one.

Nature of the Dye : The following dyes have been found to show sharp boundary formation as described above : Xyloidine ponceau, Evan's blue, Direct sky blue; Direct violet, Isamin blue, Coomassie navy blue, 2RNS, Chlorantine fast yellow, Chlorazol rose BS, Alkali blue 6B, Alphazurine FG, Celliton fast orange GR, Celliton blue extra, Celliton fast red violet RN, Cibacron blue 2D, Cotton blue and a few others. Some other sulphonic acid dyes besides the above-mentioned ones also show boundary formation but rather of a faint and diffuse type while a large number of others have practically no such tendency. This does not mean that these dyes are incapable of boundary formation it may quite well be, as has been observed in some cases, that a change of concentration, ionic strength or pH or an inordinately long time may make these dyes boundary-producing. However, all our detailed work has been done with the two acid dyes, xyloidine ponceau and Evan's blue

firstly because they do not change colour with change of pH and secondly because they represent more or less two extremes in behaviour. Evan's blue shows much quicker boundary formation and much quicker electro-bleaching under otherwise identical conditions than xylidine ponceau. It may be pointed out that some of the above-listed dyes are non-ionic (for example the celliton dyes) but we are not too sure whether the commercial samples are sold as such or after sulphonation. Some vat dyes also show very sharp boundary formation.

Cationic dyes on electrolysis as above generally show ill-defined boundary of interpenetrating colours, if at all, somewhere near BB' usually between the alkali colour and the acid colour of the dye and not between two zones one of deeper colour and another of lighter colour as in the case of the above-listed dyes. However, there are some exceptions to the above generalization. For example, calcozinc brown RX , indanthrene blue GCD , celestine blue, Janus green B and some other basic dyes including a number of other calcozinc dyes show fairly sharp boundary formation as above. Crystal violet fails to give any good stable boundary either by itself or after addition of acid, base or salt, whereas methylene blue shows fairly sharp boundary formation on addition of a trace of a salt or acid. On the whole however cationic dyes have much poorer tendency to such boundary formation, and if formed, such boundaries are generally ill-defined and unstable.

Effect of Cell Geometry - (v) Double Boundary Formation: If a cell of the shape of a double bent U-tube (to be called W-tube for brevity) shown in Fig. 2 is used, two boundaries are formed instead of one, *viz.*, two coloured phases (AB and $B'C$) separated by an intermediate usually colourless phase (BB'). This may take a few hours, usually overnight or even longer. The two boundaries (B and B') are extremely sharp and flat. The portion AB evidently is a solution of the dye acid possibly with traces of the acid derived from any

Fig. 2

salt if present as impurity in the dye. Its pH is near about 2.5 or a few tenths above it. BB' is an almost neutral solution (pH : 7.5 to 8.2) and CB' is an alkaline dye solution (pH : nearabout 11.5). A good portion of the dye remains in CB' and does not appear to migrate to the anode, but if it is subjected to fresh electrolysis after separation from the rest and taken alone in any U-tube it migrates normally as described hereinbefore. So after double boundary formation the dye ions left in the cathode chamber appear to have somehow lost though only for the time being their normal tendency to migrate in an electric field. It does not matter whether the W-tube is either wholly filled with the dye solution to start with or only the cathode compartment CB' is filled with the anionic dye solution the rest being water, the result is the same as above. In fact, this is an excellent method to prepare a pure solution of the dye acid or inorganic acids of complex anions. This behaviour would be referred to as "double boundary formation".

It may be mentioned here that quite a few cationic dyes (for example, methylene blue) and conventional indicators (for example, bromothymol blue) though almost incapable of producing a sharp boundary in a simple U-tube, are quite capable of showing such double boundary formation on prolonged electrolysis. A queer observation may be mentioned in this connection. Addition of alcohol to an ordinary dye solution, say, Evan's blue, sometimes give rise to colourless rings on electrolysis at or near BB' in a simple U-tube. Such colourless ring formation in a U-tube on electrolysis is occasionally observed also under various other conditions and may be regarded as somewhat analogous to double boundary formation.

(ii) If a double bent tube with a long horizontal portion, say as long as two and a half feet, is used as the cell, the boundary appears as usual nearabout the middle of the cell somewhat nearer to the cathode side. This boundary is seen sometimes to move forward and backward slowly for quite some time before assuming its steady equilibrium position. This result shows that gravity has nothing to do with the reported boundary formation and subsequent inhibition of electro-migration of the dye ion.

(iii) If a vertical tube is used with one electrode at the bottom and another at the top, hardly any boundary formation takes place under our usual conditions. This may be partly due to the disturbance caused by the rising bubbles of gas, albeit very few, liberated on the electrode at the bottom, but this does not appear to be the whole truth. Under such condition the dye solution as a whole gets progressively bleached.

(iv) The narrower the U-tube the quicker is the boundary formation. Thus, with a 22 mm O.D. U-type (30 cm height) and a current strength of 2 milliamperes, the boundary takes more than an hour for xylydine ponceau to appear sharply whereas with a 12 mm O.D. U-tube, it takes less than ten minutes. The latter or smaller size is thus very convenient for lecture demonstration of both single and double boundary formation.

Electrolysis of Ordinary Salts : Not only dyes but dilute solutions of many inorganic salts show such boundary and double boundary formation, for example, chromate, dichromate, ferrocyanide, ferricyanide, permanganate, etc. It appears that even dilute sodium sulphate on electrolysis in a W-tube forms double boundary as concluded from the fact that the usual three zones of three different pH are formed. It would be of interest to definitely

find out with Schlieren technique if the interzone boundaries are as sharp here as in the other cases. This fact again shows that electrolysis at low current and high dilution has many unexpected interesting features.

Experiments with the Dye Acid : The dye acid is easily obtained, as already mentioned, as a product of electrolysis in the anode compartment particularly in a W-tube, the dye solution to start with being in the cathode limb, the rest being filled up with water. If an electrolysis experiment in a U-tube is done with such dye acid solutions, the results are significantly different from that of the original dye solution. The colour from the top of the cathode limb (in other words, a sharp boundary (colourless/coloured) continually moves downwards until the position BB' is reached, and there the boundary remains stationary. This is very different from the behaviour of the solution of the original dye as follows. Firstly, during the electrolysis of the original dye solution the boundary forms at BB' and at no stage may be said to have moved towards BB' whereas in the case of the acid dye or acidified dye solution the boundary starts moving from the top and moves on until it reaches the limiting position BB'. Secondly, in the former case the boundary is between a deeper coloured anodic solution and a lighter coloured cathode solution, whereas in the latter case it is colourless upon coloured.

If the dye acid solution whose pH is about 2.5 is neutralised to a pH of about 7, its visible transport behaviour on electrolysis is more or less the same as that of the original dye solution. Evidently, the pH and the counterions play a definite role in production of the boundary at or near BB'. The following points are worthy of notice.

(i) Though the potential gradient is between the electrodes which are quite some distance below the surface of the solution, the dye boundary starts moving right from the surface of the solution in the U-tube. The dye ions within the electric field appear to be somehow linked up with the ones outside the field, as far as ionic migration is concerned.

(ii) If a layer of water is placed on the acid dye solution, the thermal diffusion rate is very slow as for any other solution; very little intermixing takes place say in a day or two. However, if the boundary is produced by electric current and the current is switched off, the two layers interdiffuse much faster and become homogeneous overnight. This type of behaviour as already mentioned, is also shown by the original dye solution, but this intermixing by diffusion is much faster in the case of the original dye solution.

Mechanism of Boundary Formation : It is well-known² in colloid chemistry that during electrolysis stratification in layers takes place in many colloidal systems due to gravitational settling near the membrane. This is the basis of a number of electrical processes for purification and concentration of proteins and similar other colloids. A similar mechanism may be considered. The boundary may be thought to have been formed by the dye anions migrating towards the anode and forming there the dye acid after getting discharged. These dye acid molecules, probably after association to form a colloidal solution, for some not yet understood reason (which is evidently not gravity) disperse themselves throughout the anode zone AB. According to this idea the boundary is between the dye acid (which may be colloidal) and a very dilute dye solution which has become alkaline by the liberated alkali at the cathode.

Such an idea however does not explain even the basic fact why the dye anions do not migrate at all with the electric current, particularly as sulphonic acid is a strong acid; and also why added acid, alkali and salts have strong effect on the rate, sharpness and some other features of boundary formation. Micellisation may be invoked but these micelles should have some electrolytic mobility unless they are assumed to be electroneutral and hence of zero transport number. The concept of isoelectric pH is also inapplicable because the dye solutions, both AB and CB, if separated and tested in an electric field, are found to be capable of showing the usual migration of the dye ions. Thus, the above discussion throws no light on the cause of the sharp separation into two zones (three zones in the case of double boundary formation) of different pH which intermix comparatively very fast on switching off the current. Neither does it explain the puzzling fact that though the boundary is easily produced in a U-tube or a horizontal tube it has not been possible to produce it in a vertical tube.

The double boundary formation separating three zones of sharply varying pH points to the fact that the geometry of the cell is an important factor besides ionic migration. Normally, Kolrausch condition of constancy of concentration/transport number leads to sharp boundary. But here this relation is of no avail as the boundary does not move with the current. The fact that cationic dyes are also capable of boundary formation and better still double boundary formation, points to the generality of the reported behaviour and hence the need for a general explanation applicable to all kinds of dyes.

The subsequent discharge of colour of CB and later on of AB on continuation of current is also difficult to understand. It is conceivable that CB gets bleached by cathodic reduction and AB by anodic oxidation. What however is difficult to understand is how the bleaching takes place homogeneously throughout both CB and AB unless diffusion is assumed to be much faster than usual. If the current is transported wholly by ionic mechanism, as is usually supposed to be the case, the current will be predominantly carried by H^+ and OH^- ions, imparting zero transport number to the dye anions. Evidently, this can not bring about bleaching at so far away from the electrodes. There is a distinct possibility¹ that a part of the current may be passing by direct electronic mechanism at such low concentration and amperage and this may be in some way responsible for the bleaching. It is evident that migration of ions at low concentration and low current strength has a few surprising features which are hardly anticipated from and adequately described by the current idea of electrolytic conduction. Further work is in progress.

Thanks are due to Sri Prithwis Kumar Basu and Mrs. Manika Dutta Gupta for essential experimental assistance.

REFERENCES

1. S. R. Palit, *Indian J. Physics*, 1971, **45**, 575.
2. For references *vide* Organic Colloids by B. Jirgensons (Elsevier), 1958, p. 180.

